

JALON

**Regional Energy Community Project
Design**

[La Moraña (Ávila) / Spain]

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1. Context

JALON has identified a regional initiative in the Moraña district of Ávila to establish a renewable energy community (REC), which will encompass several of the region's 60 municipalities. The Ávila Provincial Council is supporting this initiative through the Provincial Energy Agency (APEA) and the Ávila Community Transformation Office (OTC). In April 2025, the JALON project organised a series of replication workshops in the Calatayud region, which were attended by several La Moraña mayors and technicians from the OTC and the Ávila Provincial Council. The meeting aimed to share JALON's experience in creating and implementing a regional rural energy community, with the intention of replicating this model in other areas such as La Moraña. Participatory meetings were held during the conference on the design of a REC, JALON's experience in villages, and the key aspects for replicating JALON in the creation and operation of large energy communities in rural areas. In addition, the delegation from Ávila visited three of JALON's projects in the municipalities of Maluenda, Bubierca and Pozuel de Ariza. During these visits, the Ávila delegation was able to learn about JALON's experiences first-hand by interacting with mayors, residents, and REC project participants.

Like the region of Calatayud, La Moraña suffers from rural depopulation, with a population density of just 15 inhabitants per square kilometre. However, if we exclude the municipality of Arévalo, which has almost 8,000 inhabitants, this figure drops to just 10 inhabitants per square kilometre. In many towns with fewer than 100 inhabitants, it is often less than six inhabitants per square kilometre. Depopulation is ingrained in La Moraña's soul. Evidence of this can be seen in the large number of 'depopulated' areas in the region, with over 150 villages having been depopulated throughout history, particularly since the Industrial Revolution.

Concerned about the future of their towns, some mayors and community leaders in the region are attempting to launch initiatives focused on creating economic activities that will slow down depopulation. One of the most noteworthy initiatives is the establishment of energy communities, which promote community spirit and social cohesion around a common goal, while offering economic benefits thanks to the generation of cheap, local energy from community renewable energy projects. However, establishing a REC from scratch in depopulated rural areas with an ageing population presents significant challenges due to the novelty of the initiative and the level of participation required. Added to this are many other barriers, such as a lack of appropriate legislation, bureaucratic obstacles to activating photovoltaic systems for collective self-consumption, the legal constitution of the REC itself and the complexities inherent in bottom-up initiatives involving real participation.

These difficulties prompted a group of mayors and technicians from the Ávila Provincial Council and the OTC to seek support from existing initiatives, such as JALON, to help promote the project in their region.

2. Scope of the project design

Background

La Moraña is a historical and predominantly rural comarca located in the northern part of the province of Ávila, within the Castile and León Region. The region covers an area of 1,669 km² and has a population of around 20,000¹. Characterized by extensive agricultural

Figure 1: La Moraña County (orange color) within the province of Ávila and its location in Spain

plains, the region faces persistent demographic, economic, and environmental challenges common to the Spanish interior.

About the social dimension, La Moraña is experiencing a sustained demographic decline, consistent with the broader depopulation affecting rural Ávila. Population loss has been significant in small municipalities, while the average age continues to rise due to youth outmigration and low birth rates. Many villages have seen population decreases exceeding 20% in recent decades, creating a demographic imbalance dominated by elderly residents². In addition, employment opportunities are limited and concentrated mainly in traditional sectors such as agriculture and small-scale services located in Arévalo and other larger towns³. Provincial labour market data from SEPE highlight lower employment and activity rates than national averages⁴. The lack of industrial or technological sectors and the prevalence of seasonal agricultural jobs exacerbate youth outmigration.

Another issue the region faces is the housing problem. Housing availability is paradoxical: while there is a high number of vacant homes in rural villages, many are in poor condition or require rehabilitation⁵. Municipal and provincial authorities have launched small-scale rehabilitation and rental promotion initiatives⁶. However, results remain uneven.

¹ ADRIMO. <https://adrimo.es/>

² 'La Moraña: estudio pueblo a pueblo.' Junta de Castilla y León / Diputación de Ávila (2022).

³ Diputación de Ávila. Comercio Rural Ávila program (2023).

⁴ SEPE. Informe del mercado de trabajo provincial: Ávila 2024.

⁵ Project Arraigo (2023). Program for Rural Reoccupation in Spain.

⁶ Diputación de Ávila & Proyecto Arraigo (2023). Collaboration for repopulation of municipalities.

On the other hand, public services are concentrated in larger localities such as Arévalo and Madrigal de las Altas Torres, while smaller villages face progressive loss of healthcare, education and administrative services⁷. Transport and digital communications remain uneven despite efforts under Next Generation EU and provincial programs⁸. ADRIMO and the Ávila Provincial Council have developed programs to improve rural commerce and maintain essential services⁹.

About the economic dimension, agriculture remains the backbone of La Moraña's economy, dominated by cereal cultivation (wheat and barley)¹⁰, facing environmental stress from climate change, land-use homogenization, and soil degradation.

In summary, the social profile of La Moraña reflects Spain's broader 'Demographic Challenge' (Reto Demográfico)¹¹: population decline, ageing, limited employment diversification, underused housing, and service centralization.

Objective

Based on the spirit of JALON, the aim of this region is to establish a REC in the **Moraña** to provide opportunities to combat climate change and rural depopulation. To such endeavour the REC will act by promoting actions specifically to give a response to the real needs of the region. These needs imply basically the reinforcement of the local actors' network to work on the social transformation of the region with the final objective of fighting against the climate change and the urban migration and abandonment of the rural area.

Concept and methodology

The implementation of the REC in La Moraña is expected to take place in three phases:

1. The 'Sowing the seed' phase. This three-year phase involves creating the REC and developing participatory processes with citizens, local councils, businesses, industries, installers and other stakeholders in the municipalities of the region.
2. PV project development. This phase begins in the second year after the establishment of the REC and overlaps with the previous phase. It lasts for three years and all projects developed in Phase 1 must be undertaken in accordance with the objectives set out in this document.
3. REC operation phase. Once Phase 2 is complete, the REC enters the PV system operation phase. During this phase, maintenance operations are carried out, the energy produced is managed in order to maximise local impact, and new projects related to renewable energy, storage, mobility, and energy efficiency are promoted.

The methodology for implementing the REC in La Moraña in Phases 1 and 2 is based on the following elements:

⁷ Diputación de Ávila. Provincial public services and rural development.

⁸ Diputación de Ávila. Next Generation and rural digitalization programs.

⁹ ADRIMO. Estrategia de Desarrollo Local Participativo 2023–2027.

¹⁰ ASAJÁvila. Ensayos y cultivos en La Moraña (2022).

¹¹ <https://www.miteco.gob.es/en/reto-demografico/secretaria-general-reto-demografico.html>

- Forming a promotional group to establish the legal framework of the REC and agree on strategic lines. This group may comprise volunteers.
- Reach 13.5% of the regional population, based on the theory of introducing innovations into society.
- Seek the cooperation of mayors and town secretaries in the towns where action is to be taken. They are key to gaining the trust of residents.
- Deploy a field team to carry out awareness-raising, commitment and training tasks through participatory processes in the towns. This team must be made up of qualified and paid staff, not volunteers.
- Involve local installers and engineers.
- Use and adapt the tools created by JALON, such as technical specifications, contracts, methodologies and statutes.
- Draw up a business plan.
- Ensure the financial sustainability of the REC.

The regional dimension of the REC is justified by its potential impact on the region, which is greater than that of other options, such as local RECs. However, the implementation of a regional REC requires a professionalised field team with a dynamic social, technical and financial profile to be present in the territory continuously. This incurs economic costs, making it necessary to establish a business plan that specifies the sources of funding and provides a clear understanding of the operating and management costs of the REC and its activities. The following sequence is therefore proposed for the design of the REC:

1. Determine the region in which the work will be carried out and establish how many municipalities it contains. Characterise the region's population, economic activities and energy needs. Identify local and regional stakeholders. It has been decided that, at this stage, the REC's objective will be to reach 50% of the localities in the region, i.e. 30 municipalities.
2. Based on the REC's objectives, establish an annual work-plan identifying how many towns will be visited, the messages to be conveyed and how residents, associations, companies and businesses will be invited to participate.
3. Based on the above, define the resources needed to carry out the fieldwork, including the number and profile of workers, vehicles and other resources required.
4. Using the above information, design a business plan for the REC that ensures its economic viability.
5. Feed back into the annual work plan the requirements established by the business plan, such as the number of participants needed by the REC, the number of PV installations required and the amount of energy to be produced.

Scope of the project

This document outlines the proposed REC design for the Moraña region. The design only addresses phases 1 and 2 defined above, and it is based on the criteria and principles established by the JALON project. Phase 3 is addressed in the REC's economic sustainability study.

Essentially, this criterion states that large-scale rural RECs have advantages over smaller, local ones, which can be summarised as follows:

- In rural areas with dispersed small villages and low population, a regional REC can have a real impact on the region, as it has the capability to develop projects in all the municipalities in the area, even in the smallest villages, where local RECs would find it difficult to establish themselves due to a lack of necessary resources.
- A regional initiative has the potential to create a sense of community, as the REC brings together regional stakeholders for a shared goal.
- Resource optimization. Centralized management consolidates expertise across technical, economic, fiscal, and administrative processes in renewable project deployment.
- Economies of scale. Centralized procurement of PV components and installation services results in more competitive prices than if the projects were implemented independently.

The JALON principles also establish the following:

- A regional REC should reach all towns.
- The REC is implemented from the bottom up by citizens, with the support of municipalities and the regional public body.
- The objectives of the REC are to:
 - combat depopulation;
 - promote territorial cohesion;
 - provide cheap, locally available, renewable energy; and
 - develop renewable energy and energy efficiency projects.
- The REC is established as an energy retailer to carry out the activities of a REC (e.g. surplus recovery and acting as a electricity market agent).

The scope of the Moraña regional REC design is defined by the following points:

- A) Legal aspects
 - a. Establishing the activities of the REC and determining their compliance with current legislation.
- B) Organizational aspects
 - a. Definition of the REC legal form.
 - b. Definition of the local team.
 - c. Identification and characterization of the target population.
 - d. Methodology to raise awareness among the population
- C) Technical aspects
 - a. Characterization of the electricity consumption.
 - b. Criteria to size the PV self-consumption systems.
 - c. Design of the PV self-consumption systems.
 - d. Definition of the operation and maintenance strategy.
- D) Financial aspects
 - a. Definition of a business plan
 - b. Definition of the financing scheme

3. Characterization of the region

Description of the target region

La Moraña region covers an area of 1,669 km² and has a population of 19,446 (2024 figure, source INE¹²) spread across 60 municipalities. The most important centre is Arévalo, which has a population of 7,830. Forty-six of the villages (76.6%) have fewer than 200 inhabitants, giving the area a population density of 0.086 inhabitants per km², one of the lowest in Spain.

Figure 2: Map of La Moraña and its villages (source <https://adrimo.es/>)

As mentioned above, La Moraña is characterised by population decline, ageing, limited employment diversification, underused housing, and service centralization.....

¹² Instituto Nacional de Estadística (INE) <https://www.ine.es/>

Characterization of electricity consumption in the region

According to data collected by Datadis¹³, the total residential electricity consumption in the region in 2024 was **26.26 GWh**, distributed across 16,105 low-voltage consumption points. The municipality of **Arévalo** accounted for **37.36%** of this consumption. The average consumption per household in 2024 was 1,631 kWh, representing 46% of the Spanish average for residential consumption¹⁴, i.e. it was very low, which is typical of rural areas with low population density.

Table 1 provides a list of the municipalities of La Moraña, alongside their residential electricity consumption in 2024, the number of electricity supply contracts, the population census, and the average electricity consumption per dwelling in each municipality:

Table 1: List of municipalities of La Moraña, and 2024 data about residential electricity consumption, number of electricity supply contracts, population census, and average electricity consumption per dwelling in each municipality

Village	2024 Residential consumption (kWh)	Nº residential contrats	Population census 2024	kWh / contract / year
ADANERO	349.987	242	208	1.446
ALBORNOS	272.474	173	175	1.575
ALDEASECA	229.596	150	203	1.531
ARÉVALO	9.811.410	5.379	7830	1.824
AVEINTE	96.670	121	73	799
BARROMÁN	209.735	142	175	1.477
BERCIAL DE ZAPARDIEL	219.650	143	173	1.536
BERNUY-ZAPARDIEL	154.386	98	84	1.575
BLASCONUÑO DE MATA CABRAS	14.353	18	14	797
BLASCOSANCHO	291.013	222	100	1.311
BOHODÓN, EL	188.977	146	110	1.294
CABEZAS DE ALAMBRE	165.334	116	153	1.425
CABEZAS DEL POZO	135.432	97	82	1.396
CABIZUELA	117.351	81	88	1.449
CANALES	53.255	32	35	1.664
CANTIVEROS	171.769	112	99	1.534
CASTELLANOS DE ZAPARDIEL	120.441	76	113	1.585
CISLA	106.943	74	102	1.445
COLLADO DE CONTIRERAS	236.537	170	145	1.391

¹³ <https://datadis.es/home>

¹⁴ Instituto para la Diversificación y el Ahorro de la Energía (IDAE) <https://informesweb.idae.es/consumo-usos-residencial/index.php>

Village	2024 Residential consumption (kWh)	Nº residential contrats	Population census 2024	kWh / contract / year
CONSTANZANA	139.806	86	99	1.626
CRESPOS	666.627	394	482	1.692
DONJIMENO	69.446	55	72	1.263
DONVIDAS	35.844	31	36	1.156
ESPINOSADE LOS CABALLEROS	102.301	70	97	1.461
FLORES DE ÁVILA	372.159	302	270	1.232
FONTIVEROS	1.022.192	557	725	1.835
FUENTE EL SAÚZ	193.202	131	151	1.475
FUENTES DE AÑO	152.071	107	88	1.421
OSO, EL	197.408	165	129	1.196
GIMIALCÓN	98.120	95	66	1.033
GOTARRENDURA	160.032	130	167	1.231
GUTIERRE-MUÑOZ	141.670	100	64	1.417
HERNANSANCHO	237.893	178	142	1.336
HORCAJO DE LAS TORRES	661.453	416	441	1.590
LANGA	541.693	286	450	1.894
MADRIGAL DE LAS ALTAS TORRES	1.732.087	1.016	1299	1.705
MAMBLAS	290.530	152	196	1.911
MORALEJA DE MATA CABRAS	86.249	63	53	1.369
MUÑOMER DEL PECO	148.965	66	111	2.257
MUÑOSANCHO	174.032	114	88	1.527
NARROS DEL CASTILLO	234.414	172	152	1.363
NARROS DE SALDUEÑA	158.893	116	106	1.370
NAVA DE ARÉVALO	841.381	512	663	1.643
ORBITA	95.054	84	69	1.132
PAJARES DE ADAJA	189.512	178	127	1.065
PALACIOS DE GODA	521.280	322	397	1.619
PAPATRIGO	386.451	268	219	1.442
PEDRO-RODRÍGUEZ	224.180	150	134	1.495
RASUEROS	284.620	284	160	1.002
RIVILLA DE BARAJAS	81.336	59	56	1.379
SALVADIÓS	125.911	118	71	1.067
SANCHIDRIÁN	1.039.234	675	708	1.540

Village	2024 Residential consumption (kWh)	Nº residential contrats	Population census 2024	kWh / contract / year
SAN ESTEBAN DE ZAPARDIEL	71.947	54	40	1.332
SAN PASCUAL	119.316	61	45	1.956
SAN VICENTE DE ARÉVALO	257.603	145	165	1.777
SINLABAJOS	161.191	113	135	1.426
TIÑOSILLOS	879.585	367	756	2.397
VILLANUEVADE GÓMEZ	181.902	172	115	1.058
VILLANUEVADEL ACERAL	175.223	86	92	2.037
VIÑEGRADE MORAÑA	63.531	63	48	1.008
Total	26.261.657	16.105	19.446	1.631

Figure 3 illustrates the evolution of aggregate residential electricity consumption across the 60 municipalities of La Moraña in 2024, with Arévalo shown separately. As can be seen, December and January are the months with the highest consumption, with a peak in spring that may be due to weather conditions. We also see that there is another, longer peak in summer.

Figure 3: Electricity consumption in La Moraña in 2024. The orange line shows the total consumption of all 60 municipalities, while the blue line shows the consumption of Arévalo only.

Identification of key stakeholders

The following stakeholders have been identified in the region:

Energy Communities stakeholders:

- Ávila OTC: <https://www.diputacionavila.es/asuntos-europeos/proyectos-nextgenerationeu/otc.html>. The Community Transformation Office (One-stop-shop) promotes and revitalises energy communities in the province of Ávila. The OTC provides free information, advice and support to individuals, businesses and public sector organisations looking to establish energy communities. The office aims to facilitate access for all citizens to different cooperative models for the collective production and consumption of renewable energy. This expands the social and environmental benefits of emission-free technologies, including cost reduction, the creation of a local community and socio-economic fabric, participatory action and direct involvement in decarbonisation and tackling the climate crisis.
- Comunidad Ciudadana de Energías Renovables Gotarrendura CunaSTeresa <https://ccecunasteresa.com/>. The Gotarrendura CunaSTeresa Renewable Energy Citizen Community in Ávila is a legally constituted, non-profit association open to all. Its aim is to offer environmental, economic and/or social benefits to its members and the localities in which it operates by generating energy from renewable sources and providing energy efficiency services, specifically photovoltaic energy, as well as distribution, supply, consumption, aggregation and storage.

Social stakeholders:

- Mancomunidad de Municipios de la Comarca de la Moraña: <https://www.mancomunidadesavila.es/mancomunidad/comarca-la-morana/municipios-que-agrupa.html>. The association of municipalities of La Moraña is a voluntary grouping of municipalities in this region that have come together to carry out joint projects and services.
- Asociación para el Desarrollo Rural Integral de la Moraña ADRIMO: <https://adrimo.es/adrimo/sobre-nosotros>. The Association for the Integral Rural Development of La Moraña (ADRIMO) aims to promote, support and encourage business and cultural activities. The Association seeks to achieve sustainable economic and social development by improving the living conditions of inhabitants of the La Moraña region, and by enabling disadvantaged groups, such as women and young people, to enter the labour market. ADRIMO currently has over 250 members, including local councils, associations, cooperatives, companies and individuals. Since 2002, ADRIMO has been responsible for managing rural development programmes co-financed by European, national, regional and local funds.

Technical stakeholders:

- I-DE Redes Eléctricas Inteligentes, S.A.U. <https://www.i-de.es/>. I-DE, part of the Iberdrola group, is the electricity distribution company operating in the province of Ávila.
- Proyecta Energía <https://proyectaenergia.com/inicio/>. Engineering consultant and installer leader in Ávila.

Public bodies:

- Agencia Provincial de la Energía de Ávila (APEA), www.apea.com.es. It promotes energy efficiency, savings and the use of renewable energies throughout the province, advising local councils, businesses and citizens.
- (Delegación Territorial de Ávila), <https://energia.jcyl.es/web/es/informacion-publica-energia-minas/energia-avila.html>. Manages the regulation, promotion and planning of energy and mining in the province of Ávila, at the regional level.
- Área de Energía / Asuntos Europeos, Energía y Turismo, <https://www.diputacionavila.es/>. The Provincial Council promotes local energy transition (e.g. rural energy communities) and technical support through the APEA.
- Municipalities of the Moraña listed in Table 1.

4. Sizing of PV systems

Initially, PV systems will be designed for self-consumption, without storage. This is to reduce the initial investment required for the REC as much as possible, given that batteries can be added in a second phase.

There are three types of PV self-consumption system:

- 1) Collective systems for residential prosumers.
- 2) Collective systems for businesses and municipal services.
- 3) Individual / collective systems for industrial use.

1) Collective systems for residential prosumers

PV systems are designed for collective rather than individual self-consumption, as this achieves economies of scale, reducing investment by up to 50%.

These collective systems are sized so that a single PV system can meet the needs of participants in a municipality. However, if the municipality is large, such as Arévalo, more than one PV system is required.

The following criteria are used to size a PV system:

- The PV system is sized to produce an annual energy output equivalent to the annual energy consumption of all participants in the collective system. This enables prosumers to achieve a self-consumption rate of 50%. If storage is added to the system in the future, the remaining 50% of energy can also be self-consumed, thus contributing to a greater local impact on REC energy usage.
- The number of participants per municipality is estimated based on the theory of innovation adoption¹⁵. This theory describes a sector of the population as 'early adopters', who are willing to adopt an innovation at an early stage of its introduction to the market. This group represents **13.5%** of the population and is the target of REC's entire communication strategy.

¹⁵ Rogers, E. M. (1962). *Diffusion of innovations*. Free Press of Glencoe

In La Moraña, 45 out of 60 municipalities (75%) have fewer than 200 residential electricity supply contracts (CUPS¹⁶). Excluding Arévalo, the average number of electricity supply contracts per municipality is 182. Applying a 13.5% early adopter rate to this number of contracts suggests that the average number of REC participants per municipality is **25 CUPS**. Similarly, the average annual energy consumption per household is **1,631 kWh**, meaning that PV systems must, on average, be sized to produce:

$$E_{PV-y} = 1,631 \text{ (kWh/year)/household} \times 25 \text{ households} = 40,775 \text{ kWh/year}$$

The PV system must produce approximately 40.77 MWh of electricity per year. The productivity of a PV system installed on a fixed structure on a south-facing roof with a 30° slope is 1,550 kWh/kWp. Therefore, to produce 40.77 MWh, a PV system with a peak power of **26.3 kWp** is required:

$$P_{Peak1} = \frac{40,775 \text{ kWh}}{1,550 \text{ kWh/kWp}} = 26.30 \text{ kWp}$$

The REC's objective in this stage is to reach 50% of the region's towns, i.e. 30 municipalities. This would entail carrying out **30 projects**, each with an average power of **26.30 kWp**, totalling **789 kWp** of installed PV power.

2) Collective systems for businesses and municipal services

Collective self-consumption PV systems are planned for local shops, small businesses and municipal services in the six largest municipalities in terms of population: Arévalo (5,379 inhabitants), Madrigal de las Altas Torres (1,299 inhabitants), Tiñosillos (756 inhabitants), Fontiveros (725 inhabitants), Sanchidrián (708 inhabitants) and Nava de Arévalo (663 inhabitants). The same criteria will be used as for residential consumption. It is estimated that an average of three small businesses or local shops and one town hall will participate per municipality, with an average daily consumption of 50 kWh each. This adds up to an average daily consumption of 200 kWh per village. This results in a total annual energy consumption of 73 MWh per village.

The PV system is sized to produce the same amount of energy per year as is consumed by all participants in the collective system annually. Considering an average productivity of 1,550 kWh/kWp for a PV system on a fixed structure with a 30° tilt angle and facing south, the average peak PV power required for each municipality will be 47.1 kWp:

$$P_{Peak2} = \frac{73,000 \text{ kWh}}{1,550 \text{ kWh/kWp}} = 47.1 \text{ kWp}$$

The total power for the six municipalities is **282.6 kWp**.

3) Individual / collective systems for industrial use

The objective is to install PV systems for individual or collective self-consumption with a nominal power of 100 kW in ten small and medium-sized local industries. This power rating was chosen due to the available roof space and, above all, Spanish regulations that stipulate this maximum power rating for a PV self-consumption installation to qualify for

¹⁶ Código Universal del Punto de Suministro: Meter Point Administration Number

self-consumption with surplus and simplified compensation. This mechanism enables producers to offset surplus energy fed into the grid against their electricity bill, providing an economic balance of the energy consumed during the billing period.

Assuming a system productivity of 1,550 kWh/kWp, each of these PV systems will have the capacity to produce 155 MWh/year.

The total installed capacity across the ten industries will be **1,000 kWp**.

The PV systems at REC La Moraña are summarised in Table 2:

Table 2: Summary of PV self-consumption systems for the Moraña REC

Type of PV system	Average power per system	Number of systems	Total power (kWp)	Number of beneficiaries
1) Collective for residential	26.3	30	789	750 households
2) Collective for local shops and municipalities	47.1	6	282.6	18 local shops y 6 councils
3) Individual or collective for industries	100	10	1,000	10 industries

The total installed PV power is **2,071.6 kWp**.

Regarding collective residential PV systems, the average number of people per dwelling in La Moraña is 2.5, meaning the PV installations will impact **1,875 people**.

5. Financial model

This section outlines both the REC's investment needs and the financial instruments required to cover the REC's investments.

The financial model is established for the two phases of the REC's implementation, as outlined in the Concept and methodology section:

1. 'Sowing the seed' phase. This three-year phase involves establishing the REC and developing participatory processes with citizens, local councils, businesses, industries, installers and other stakeholders in the municipalities of the region. During this period, funding is needed to cover the costs of communication tasks for the REC.
2. PV project development phase. This phase begins in year two from the establishment of the REC and therefore overlaps with the previous phase. Investments in this phase are exclusively aimed at covering the costs of PV projects.

1. Seeding the idea phase

The costs associated with this activity are made up of the following components:

- a. Staff: a professional field team consisting of two people with social, technical and financial profiles. Both will have a gross annual salary of €37,000 (full-time equivalent).

- b. Transport: a vehicle to increase presence in the territory. Average annual cost: €7,200.
- c. Office equipment: PC and internet connection for remote working. Average annual cost: €1,000.
- d. Telephone: Average annual cost: €500
- e. Communication materials: brochures, posters, signs, videos, photos, etc. Average annual cost: €2,000.
- f. Other communication tools, such as the creation of a REC website, social media accounts and participation in forums, cost €1,000 in total.

The annual costs of these items are summarised below:

	Annual cost
a. Personnel (staff)	€74,500 €
b. Transport	€7,200 €
c. Office equipment	€1,000 €
d. Telephone	€500 €
e. Communication materials	€2,000 €
f. Other communication tools (web, social media, etc)	€1,000 €
TOTAL	€85,700 €

Therefore, this phase will require an annual budget of €85,700 for one of each three years, **totalling €257,100.**

This cost must be financed through non-repayable public funding.

2. PV project development phase

The investment costs of a PV self-consumption installation must cover the following items:

- a. PV generator, consisting of PV modules, support structure and electrical connections.
- b. Grid connection inverter(s).
- c. Electrical system consisting of DC and AC power lines, electrical protection, earthing and metering cabinet.
- d. Monitoring and communication systems.
- e. Radiation and temperature sensors.
- f. Installation and issuance of electrical installation certificate.
- g. Licences.
- h. Engineering for the preparation and approval of the technical project for the installation and, where applicable, inspection carried out by an authorised control body (OCA).
- i. Activation of self-consumption and registration of the installation in the electricity self-consumption register.

Thanks to JALON, we now have market cost data for PV installations of this type. These costs, updated to 2025, can be found in Table 3:

Table 3: costes unitarios de las instalaciones FV

PV power (kWp)	Unit cost (€/kWp)
3	2,34
15	1,34
60	0,897

These references are used to construct a cost model based on peak power, as shown in Figure 4:

Figure 4: Cost trend curve for a PV installation, based on peak power.

Based on this installation cost model, it is estimated that the installation costs for the PV systems designed for La Moraña are as follows:

Table 4: Costes de las instalaciones FV de la REC

Type of PV system	Mean PV power per system (kWp)	System cost (€)	Number of PV systems	Total cost (€)
1) Collective for residential	26.3	30,247.21	30	907,416
2) Collective for local shops and municipalities	47.1	44,927.95	6	269,568
3) Individual or collective for industries	100	74,909.24	10	749,092
TOTAL				1,926,076

The total investment cost is **€1,926,076**.

The proposed financial plan for this investment is as follows:

- 60% through micro-investments made by project participants who will also be future prosumers.
- 40% through non-repayable public grants, if available.
- 21% corresponds to VAT paid in advance by project participants, which is refunded once recovered (for terms of less than one year).

The 40% subsidy would be financed by a bridge loan, which would cover that portion of the investment until the public subsidy is received (1 or 2 years).

If no public subsidies are available, an external investor, such as a bank or a crowdlending platform, would cover this portion of the investment.

The energy savings generated by the PV systems and the sale of surpluses would cover all financial costs and interest generated by external financing.

6. Business plan

The business plan has been drawn up to ensure the financial viability of the REC during Phase 3 of its operations.

It is based on the premise that energy generated by PV systems for self-consumption, developed by the REC, must contribute to its financial sustainability, as well as generating economic, social and environmental benefits for its members. Therefore, quotas have been set for PV production and deducted from prosumers' savings, without endangering the viability of their micro-investments. These quotas are intended to cover the REC's operating costs.

The criteria for drawing up the business plan are defined below.

Income of the REC

INPUTS:

Collective residential PV systems

Number of systems	30	30 villages in the Moraña region.
Mean PV power / system (kWp)	26.3	Average power per collective self-consumption PV system.
PV production Ratio (kWh/kWp)	1,550	Annual production ratio of a PV installation on a roof in Moraña facing pure south and at 30° tilt angle.

Commercial and municipal PV systems

Number of systems	6	6 villages in the Moraña region.
Mean PV power / system (kWp)	47.1	Average power per collective self-consumption PV system.
PV production Ratio (kWh/kWp)	1,550	Annual production ratio of a PV installation on a roof in Moraña facing pure south and at 30° tilt angle.

Industrial PV systems

Number of systems	10	10 industries in the Moraña region.
Mean PV power / system (kWp)	100	Average power per individual or collective self-consumption PV system.
PV production Ratio (kWh/kWp)	1,550	Annual production ratio of a PV installation on a roof in Moraña facing pure south and at 30° tilt angle.

REC participant target:

Households	750
Commercial and municipal	24
Industries	10

Annual fees:

1. Energy producers' fees (per kWh produced)		
Collective residential PV systems (€/kWh)	0,03	PV production fee.
Commercial and municipal PV systems (€/kWh)	0,03	
Industrial PV systems (€/kWh)	0,03	
2. Energy consumers' fees (per contract)		
Households (€/year)	10	Annual fee for contracting electricity supply with REC.
Commercial and municipal (€/year)	15	
Industries (€/year)	20	

Membership fees:

Households (€)	100	One-time membership fee to join the REC.
Commercial and municipal (€)	100	
Industries (€)	100	

RESULTS:

Total PV power installed		
Collective residential PV systems	789	
Commercial and municipal PV systems	283	
Industrial PV systems	1,000	
TOTAL (kWp)	2,072	

ENERGY generated annually		
Roof-tops (kWp/year)	1,222,950	
Small group PV (kWp/year)	438,030	
Medium-size PV plants (kWp/year)	1,550,000	
TOTAL (kWh/year)	3,210,980	

REC REVENUES		
1. Energy producers' fees (per kWh produced)		
Collective residential PV systems (€/kWh)	36,689	
Commercial and municipal PV systems (€/kWh)	13,141	
Industrial PV systems (€/kWh)	46,500	
TOTAL (€/year)	96,329	
2. Energy consumers' fees		
Households (€/year)	7,500	
Commercial and municipal (€/year)	360	
Industries (€/year)	200	
TOTAL (€/year)	8,060	
TOTAL REC REVENUES (€/year)	104,389	

Membersgip fees (Paid once to join the REC)		
Households (€)	75,000	
Commercial and municipal (€)	2,400	
Industries (€)	1,000	
TOTAL (€)	78,400	

Expenses of the REC

INPUTS

1. Maintenance of PV systems (€/MWp/year)	5,000	
Annual cost (€/year)	10,358	
2. Energy retailer Back-office (€/contrac/year)	10	
Annual cost (€/year)	7,840	
3. Mobility		
Vehicle renting + fuel (€/month)	600	
Annual cost (€/year)	7,200	
4. Personnel		
Employees	2.0	
Gross annual salary (€/year)	37,000	
Annual cost (€/year)	74,000	
5. Administrative & management expenses (€/year)	5,219	5% of income
TOTAL (€/year)	104,617	

Balance

The balance sheet results after tax are:

Year	Result	Year	Result
1	-€31,420	11	€3,398
2	€7,022	12	€3,398
3	€13,412	13	€3,398
4	€13,394	14	€3,398
5	€3,398	15	€3,398
6	€3,398	16	€3,398
7	€3,398	17	€3,398
8	€3,398	18	€3,398
9	€3,398	19	€3,398
10	€3,398	20	€3,398
Total		€56,772	

This balance results in an **IRR of 20.80%**.

7. Legal aspects

The decision is made to establish the REC as a non-profit cooperative in accordance with the regulations of the Castile and León Region. The REC of La Moraña has access to the statutes and internal regulations of the REC of JALON in order to adapt them to its own circumstances.

8. Methodology for engagement

The methodology for generating engagement in the region and raising awareness among various groups, such as citizens, associations, local shops, local councils and small businesses, will be based on JALON's results.

9. Conclusions

The REC La Moraña proposed in this design is summarised below:

- Size of the REC (number of participants), of which:
 - Villages of the county: 36
 - Citizens: 750 households impacting 1.875 people.
 - Local shops: 24.
 - Industries: 10.
 - Local councils: 6.
- Type and number of self-consumption PV systems:
 - Residential collective systems: 30 PV installations without storage, with an average power of 26.3 kWp (total power of 789 kWp).
 - Local shops and municipal buildings collective systems: 6 PV installations without storage, with an average power of 47,1 kWp (total power of 283 kWp).
 - Industrial self-consumption PV systems: 10 PV installations without storage, with an average power of 100 kWp (total power of 1000 kWp).

Total: **46 PV installations** without storage, with a total power output of **2,072 kWp**.

The 46 installations produce **3,211 MWh** of energy annually.

- Number of electricity consumption points supplied with energy by REC:
 - Households: **750**.
 - Local shops: **24**.
 - Industries: **10**.
 - Local councils: **6**.
- Needed investment for:
 - Phase 1. Seeding the idea (years one-to-three): €85,700 /year x 3 years = **€257,100**.
 - Phase 2: Development of PV projects (years two-to-four): **€1,926,076**.
- Funding:
 - Phase 1: Seeding the idea: **€257,100**. Non-repayable public funding.
 - Phase 2: Development of PV projects (Years 2–4): **€1,926,076**.
 - 60% from microcredits provided by project participants and beneficiaries of PV self-consumption systems.
 - 40% from non-repayable public funding, or crowdlending platform credit or similar, where applicable
 - 21% corresponding to VAT paid in advance by project participants, which is refunded once recovered.
- REC structure:
 - Legal: non-profit cooperative
 - Electricity supplier.
 - Resources:
 - Staff: 2 full-time employees who between them cover the roles of social facilitator, technician, administrator and financial officer.
 - Mobility: 1 vehicle.

- PV system maintenance service.
- Back-office service for the REC as an electricity supplier.

➤ Business plan:

- The REC charges fees to project participants:
 - PV energy production fee: **€0.03/kWh** produced.
 - Energy supply fee:
 - Housing: **€10/year**.
 - Business/town hall: **€15/year**.
 - Industry: **€20/year**.
 - REC membership fee: **€100**.

These fees represent annual income for the REC of **€104,389/year** plus membership fees totalling **€78,400**.

- The REC has operating and management expenses of **€104,617/year**.

These figures generate a positive cash flow. Over a period of two years, this represents an **IRR of 20.8%**, which ensures the financial sustainability of the REC.